

Phase 1 simulations, including HighResMIP and CMIP6 PI-control simulations

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Executive Summary

EERIE is producing two main phases of coupled model simulation, Phase 1 and Phase 2. This document will summarise the Phase 1 simulations, which include CMIP6 HighResMIP-style simulations from three EERIE groups, and several parts of a CMIP6-style simulation from one EERIE group. There are some very promising results in the model simulations, after considerable challenges in configuring these models to produce good simulations on decadal to centennial timescales.

The data available from the simulations, and some basic analysis, is also documented. More detailed analysis of these simulations will follow in future deliverables, such as D6.1.

1 Phase 1 simulation description

The Phase 1 simulations for EERIE were defined in the Description of Action. We are using two different simulation designs to complement each other and enable different but comparative analyses.

The CMIP6 HighResMIP simulations (Haarsma et al. 2016) require relatively few model simulation years, mainly due to using a given ocean initial condition representative of 1950 and a short spin-up of the coupled system (*spinup-1950*, typically 30–50 years). This means that the models will not be in equilibrium (due mainly to an ocean that will drift from these initial conditions), though parallel simulations using both constant 1950's forcings (*control-1950*) and time-varying forcings (*hist-1950*) can be used to diagnose some of this drift. Relatively short simulations enable higher resolution (smaller grid-spacing) models to be used, giving us insight into how this might change our understanding of climate variability and change. However, the relatively short length of simulation (1950–2050) means that using such models to understand longer-term variability (decadal and longer) is difficult. The total length of the HighResMIP simulations is typically 250 years (spinup-1950+control-1950+hist-1950).

In contrast, the CMIP6-style simulations require a long pre-industrial spin-up of the model using 1850's forcings (here 240 years have been used for *piSpinup*, though considerably longer is often used by groups), in order to bring the coupled system into a (quasi-)equilibrium. At this point a long simulation using the pre-industrial forcing (*piControl*) is initialised, typically 500 years but here shortened to 200 years. After this, historical (*historical*, 1850-2014) and a choice of future scenario (*sspX-xx*, 2015-2100) simulations are successively initialised. As such, these simulations typically require ~1000 years of simulation (here ~700 years), hence 3–4x those of HighResMIP. However, the length of the simulations do enable more detailed analysis of longer-term variability (particularly in the “unforced” piControl experiment), and it is somewhat easier to put future (anthropogenically-forced) periods in context compared to (unforced) pre-industrial periods.

Some simple diagrams of the simulation designs are shown on the website: <https://eerie-project.eu/research/modelling/simulations-descriptions/>

The Phase 1 model simulations comprise:

HighResMIP coupled model simulations following the CMIP6 HighResMIP protocol Haarsma et al. (2016), using the models and simulations shown in Table 1 from groups: AWI (IFS-FESOM2), MPI-M (ICON) and BSC (IFS-NEMO). These simulations are ongoing, and an up-to-date view of the completion can be found at the progress bar:

<https://eerie-project.eu/research/modelling/progress-of-simulations/>

Models	spinup-1950 (years)	control-1950 (years)	hist-1950 (years)	highres-future (years)
IFS-FESOM2, IFS-NEMO, ICON	50	100	1950-2014 (65)	2014-2050 (36)

Table 1.1: Phase 1 HighResMIP simulations.

For the Met Office, the Phase 1 simulations are the CMIP6 DECK coupled model simulations, at three different resolutions (Table 2), with the piControl being completed as part of the Phase 1 deliverable:

Model resolutions	piSpinup (>=200 years)	piControl (200+ years)	historical (1850-2014)	future (2015-2100+)
UM-NEMO-SI3 (Met Office)	240 years	200 years	165 years	85 years
N96-O1 (130km-100km)	Complete	Complete	Complete x2	Complete x2
N216-O025 (60km-25km)	Complete	Complete	Complete	Complete
N640-O12 (20km-8km)	Complete	Complete	See progress bar	See progress bar

Table 1.2: Phase 1 CMIP6 simulations.

The progress of all these simulations is available from the [EERIE website](#), as well as the details of the [model resolutions and other model aspects](#). As of September 2024, all of the groups performing the HighResMIP simulations have completed the spinup-1950 experiment, with other simulations ongoing.

2 Description of models and initial assessment

2.1 HighResMIP simulations

2.1.1 IFS – common elements

The IFS code used for the atmosphere-only and coupled simulations for EERIE is defined using the ifs-bundle tag “DE_CY48R1.0_EERIE_20240726”, which includes among others the source code (ifs-source), data encoding (eccodes), as well as the tools to run the simulations (RAPS) and the output specification (RAPS, MultIO).

2.1.2 AWI – IFS-FESOM

In AWI, the coupled climate model IFS-FESOM is used to perform the Phase 1 frontier HighResMIP type simulations. The IFS model operates at a Tco1279 resolution, which corresponds to a horizontal resolution of 9 km and includes 137 vertical levels. It is coupled with version 2.5 of the FESOM (Finite Element Sea Ice Ocean Model), configured with an NG5 unstructured triangular grid and 70 depth levels. This configuration provides a minimum horizontal resolution of 5 km in eddy-rich mid- and high-latitude regions and a resolution of approximately 13 km over the tropics (Rackow et al., 2024).

2.1.2.1 AWI – IFS-FESOM results

One primary aim of the EERIE project is to resolve the Ocean eddies in the climate model and understand its potential impact on our climate system. The snapshot of ocean currents from the coupled spin-up simulations displays the formation of Ocean eddies especially over the eddy-rich regions (such as Gulf Stream regions), indicating that the model is able to perform and simulate eddies (Figure 2.1.2.1.1).

Figure 2.1.2.1.1: A snap of the ocean eddies in an EERIE IFS-FESOM simulation. Ocean current speed at 50m depth of the Ocean (logarithmic scale) over the North Atlantic in a day during the IFS-FESOM spinup-1950 simulation using the NG5 ocean grid.

Our coupled spin-up simulation has initially shown a drift towards colder global mean surface air temperature (GMST) which apparently stabilised after the 10–15 years (Figure 2.1.2.1.2). As the simulations go on, this cold drift reduces and the global mean temperature almost returns to its initial state by the end of the simulation. This drift in GMST is mainly a result of excessive sea ice formation over the Arctic and over the Norwegian Sea (not shown). This excessive sea ice formation is likely the result of the sea ice coupling in the model where the atmosphere model assumes a constant thickness of sea ice and drives the fluxes unrealistically (this has been elaborated further afterwards in the description of IFS-NEMO which used the same methodology for atmosphere-sea ice coupling). However, over a longer period this bias reduces, the model becomes more balanced and the sea ice amount seems to get back to the expected level. However, the long-term consequences of such bias on the climate system are still to be determined when the entire centennial scale simulation is completed. Nevertheless, this issue has prompted us already to implement a more realistic sea ice coupling in Phase 2.

Figure 2.1.2.1.2: *The yearly global mean 2 metre air temperature time series for the entire period of coupled spinup-1950 of IFS-FESOM at Tco1279-NG5 atmosphere-ocean resolution and under control-1950 radiative forcing condition. Each dot represents the yearly mean temperature of each year and the x-axis represents the number of years it has simulated starting from 1950. Units are in degree Celsius.*

After completing the 50-year coupled spin-up, the simulations were extended to perform the HighResMIP Historical and Control runs, which are currently ongoing. Here, we present results from the first 30 years of these simulations. The global mean surface air temperature (GMST) remains stable during this period in both the Historical and Control simulations, and the GMST evolution in the Historical simulation aligns well with that observed in the ERA5 reanalysis (Figure 2.1.2.1.3). Examining the spatial bias in the 30-year GMST climatology compared to ERA5, we find minimal differences between the model and observations across most parts of the world (Figure 2.1.2.1.4). However, certain regions, particularly near the poles, exhibit significant temperature biases. The cold bias over the Nordic Seas is a remnant of the cold drift observed during the spin-up, which is related to the sea ice coupling strategy used in the model. Additionally, there is a large warm bias over Antarctica, associated with near-total melting of Antarctic Sea ice during the summer. This sea ice loss may also be linked to the treatment and coupling of sea ice within this model and this is presently being investigated.

Figure 2.1.2.1.3: The global annual mean 2 metre air temperature time series for the first 30 years (1950 to 1979) of ongoing CMIP6 HighResMIP Historical (in Blue) and Control (in Green) simulations of IFS-FESOM2 at Tco1279-NG5 atmosphere-ocean resolution and the time-series of the same from ERA5 reanalysis (in Orange). Each dot represents the yearly mean temperature of each year and the x-axis represents the number of years it has simulated starting from 1950. Units are in degrees Celsius.

Figure 2.1.2.1.4: The bias in the climatology of the annual mean 2 metre temperature in the Historical (left) and in the Control (right) simulation of IFS-FESOM from the ERA5 reanalysis for the time-period 1950 to 1979. The Units are in degrees Celsius.

Regarding the overall ocean eddy characteristic, the model seems to give promising results with almost identical representations of eddy-rich regions (Figure 2.1.2.1.5a,b). The main difference still remains over the Gulf Stream region where the eddy activity, although well captured, is still underestimated. This has been not entirely a surprise as this region remains one of the toughest to simulate accurately. This result provides a promising start of the project where we will be focusing on what these eddies do to our climate system.

Figure 2.1.2.1.5: *The daily SSH standard deviation over the first 20-year period in IFS-FESOM Tco1279-NG5 HighResMIP Historical simulation (top-left) and in AVISO (top-right) highlighting the ocean eddy-rich regions.*

2.1.3 MPI-M – ICON

ICON as set up for EERIE uses the R2B9 (~5km ocean with 72 levels) coupled to R2B8 (~10km atmosphere with 90 levels) configuration. Although in terms of resolution EERIE's ICON configuration is unique, with respect to other aspects of the set-up such as physics or parameterizations we have tried to stay as close as possible to the NextGEMS development.

Until the beginning of 2024, we used the coupled ICON, which has an energy leak of about 6 W/m² at the top of the atmosphere. This version produced a cooler but stable climate. We obtained 40-years of control simulation output that was used for both EERIE and nextGEMS/EERIE hackathon. Recent model development at MPIM but through the nextGEMS project produced an improved version of ICON atmosphere that we have decided to adopt and make them consistent with other projects like nextGEMS and DestinE. After spinning up the model again, this time with the improved version of the atmosphere, as of today, we have integrated a new control run for 32 years. Application of the new ICON code delivered a much more reasonable climate but led to a decrease in computational throughput from peak values with the old code of about 1.33 SYPD to about 0.75 SYPD. Repeating spin-up and control run with a reduced throughput on top put us behind schedule for the production of EERIE phase 1 simulations.

2.1.3.1 MPI-M – ICON results

As a climatically-stable (climate-ready) control simulation is crucial for having long-integration climate runs and for assessing changes in a warming world, we had decided to implement a new

version of ICON atmosphere and spun up the coupled system again followed by a new control-1950 (1950-forcing) run (see above).

Figure 2.1.3.1 shows global mean sea surface temperature (SST) in the old and new spin-up and control runs. Whereas SST displays remarkable cooling tendencies in the old runs it appears much more stable in the new spin-up and control. Global SST went up to well beyond 18 degrees Celsius (degC) in the spin-up followed by a slight drop below 18 degC just before the transition from spin-up to control run (in 1991). The drop most likely is the consequence of a bug fix in aerosol treatment in the model. Global mean 2m air temperatures show essentially the same tendencies as their SST counterparts (not shown). In the old runs, cooling tendencies were also reflected in the evolution of total ocean heat content; here, the new runs reveal a warming trend instead, which moderates from 1991 onward (Fig. 2.1.3.2). Whereas in the old runs top of the atmosphere (TOA) short wave and long wave net fluxes were too low (not shown) and out of balance by about 6 W/m², in the new runs, those fluxes appear to be much better in balance by about one order of magnitude (Fig. 2.1.3.3).

Figure 2.1.3.1: Evolution of global mean sea surface temperature in degrees Celsius, time series of monthly means with (bold) and without (thin) smoothing by a running mean in the old (blue) and new (red) control-1950 runs with respective spin-ups up front (black).

Figure 2.1.3.2: Evolution of global ocean heat content in 10^{25} J, time series of monthly means with a smoothing by a running mean in the old (blue) and new (red) control-1950 runs with respective spin-ups up front (black).

Figure 2.1.3.3: Evolution of top of the atmosphere (TOA) short wave (SW) and long wave net fluxes in $W m^{-2}$, time series of monthly means with a smoothing by a running mean in the old (blue) and new (red) control-1950 runs with respective spin-ups up front (black).

2.1.4 BSC – IFS-NEMO

This model combines the ocean component NEMO (version 4.0.7; Madec et al., 2019) and the new sea ice model SI3 (Vancoppenolle et al., 2023) with the atmospheric model IFS, in the EERIE configuration (DE_CY48R1.0_EERIE_20240726), set up with 137 vertical levels. The high-resolution EERIE version uses a triangular–cubic–octahedral horizontal grid with a grid spacing of ~10 km in the atmosphere (Tco1279) and a tripolar global orthogonal curvilinear mesh with a horizontal ocean resolution of 1/12° (eORCA12). An intermediate-resolution configuration, featuring a Tco399 grid in the atmosphere (~28 km) and eORCA025 (1/4°) in the ocean, is also employed for testing model developments and tuning choices; this version will also provide lower-resolution counterparts for the EERIE experiments. The time steps, throughput and nodes used to run the experiments at each resolution are detailed in Table 2.4.1.1.

Model resolution	Timestep (atm/ocn)	Throughput	Nodes (cores)
Intermediate Resolution: Tco399 (28 km) ORCA025 (0.25°)	15 / 20 min	~ 4 SYPD	24 (1,792)
High Resolution: Tco1279 (9 km) ORCA12 (1/12°)	7.5 / 6 min	~1.95 SYPD	213 (23,856)

Table 2.1.4.1: *Some model details for the IFS-NEMO-EERIE model simulations. This number of nodes corresponds to the optimal configuration in terms of time-to-solution in the CPU partition of Mare Nostrum 5, the current supercomputer at the BSC (36 processors/node).*

The three components are coupled through a single executable approach (Mogensen et al 2012), allowing them to run together using a common time step loop. This tightly integrated setup enables highly efficient, low-latency data exchange, which is critical for high-resolution, fully coupled simulations. The coupling operates at a 1-hour frequency, exchanging essential fields—such as sea surface temperature (SST), surface fluxes, ice cover, and ocean currents—between IFS and NEMO to capture dynamic interactions among the atmosphere, ocean, and sea ice. In the Phase 1 simulations, the specific implementation used to couple the atmosphere with the sea ice follows the standard IFS approach, in which only sea-ice concentrations are sent from SI3 to IFS. In this approach, also known as fractional coupling, IFS computes the net air – sea ice fluxes using climatological albedos for the sea ice, and ice surface temperatures (IST) assessed from its own sea-ice surface module, via an intra-ice pack conductive flux that always assume constant 1.5m thick ice. The obtained IST (which is different from SI3's) is then used by the IFS surface scheme to obtain the net non-solar air-sea ice heat flux, which is then sent to SI3 and used as a top boundary condition by SI3. This crude representation, developed by ECMWF for short coupled model integrations, has been discovered to be unsuitable to run climate scale simulations, as it leads to a sustained growth in Arctic Sea ice volume that eventually generates numerical instabilities (more

details in the results section). An alternative scheme, in which thermodynamic aspects are also involved in the coupling, has also been developed by ECMWF, but was initially discarded because its scientific validity was still to be assessed at eddy-resolving scales. In this approach the IFS sea-ice module is disabled, and it is SI3 that sends sea-ice concentrations, albedo and IST fields to IFS, which uses them to directly compute the air–sea ice surface fluxes.

The ocean and sea ice components are initialised in the same way. The initial conditions for the spinup-1950 simulation come from the final state of an ocean-sea ice standalone reconstruction, forced with ERA5 surface variables from the period 1950-1954 and initialised itself from 1950 ocean temperature and salinity fields of the ocean analysis EN4 (Good et al., 2013). Its atmospheric initial conditions are from ERA5 in 2020, which corresponds to a warmer state than 1950, although we deem this to have a small impact on the coupled system given the small heat capacity of the atmosphere. Both the control-1950 and hist-1950 simulations start from the end of the spinup-1950 run.

2.1.4.1 BSC – IFS-NEMO results

Due to the aforementioned issues with the atmospheric-sea ice coupling approach used in the Phase 1 configuration of IFS-NEMO, only part of the HighResMIP experimental protocol has been completed. This includes the full spinup-1950 simulation, 6.5 years of the control-1950, and 9.5 years of the historical runs. By the end of the spin-up, sea ice volume had increased to overly large values (Figure 2.1.4.1, top panel). This problem exacerbates in the historical and control-1950 simulation, affecting in particular a region north of Canada located around one of the two Northern poles characteristic of the eORCA grids (Figure 2.1.4.1, bottom left panel). This eventually led to a numerical instability in the sea ice velocity fields, where a distinct chequered pattern suggests the presence of spurious effects related to the North Pole folding (Figure 2.1.4.1, bottom right panel), which might be behind the instability.

Fig. 2.1.4.1.1: (Top) Timeseries of the total Arctic Sea ice volume in the spinup-1950 simulation of IFS-NEMO, with the corresponding values for the sea ice reanalysis PIOMAS provided as a reference. (Bottom left) Snapshot of the sea ice thickness in the last chunk of the historical IFS-NEMO simulation (corresponding to June 1956) before the numerical instability develops. (Bottom right) Snapshot of the vertical sea ice velocities in the region in which the numerical instability develops in the last chunk before its occurrence.

Due to this problem, which is inherent to the current sea ice coupling approach and preconditions the model to develop numerical instabilities, we decided to stop the historical simulation and to start a new spinup-1950 experiment using the new thermodynamic atmosphere-sea ice coupling instead, as some tests performed with it at the intermediate resolution version of IFS-NEMO show much better performance in terms of sea ice thickness and volume, with values that are much closer to observations (Figure 2.1.4.1.2). This new spin up run has just been launched and at the moment has completed 12 simulated years, with a throughput of nearly 2 simulated years per day. If this new model version effectively resolves the previous issues, we aim to produce with it at least the HighResMIP spinup-1950, control-1950 and hist-1950 simulations, which could be completed by spring 2025 if everything goes smoothly. As for the associated scenario run, we could also run it if both supercomputing and human resources allow it, although we will give priority to the Phase 2 simulations, which might need to start around that time to be completed on time for performing their corresponding scientific analyses.

Figure 2.1.4.1.2: (Top) Snapshot of the sea ice thickness in year 2036 of two control-1990 experiments conducted with the intermediate resolution of IFS-NEMO, one using the fractional (left) and another using the thermodynamic (right) atmospheric-sea ice coupling. (Bottom) Evolution of the total Arctic Sea ice volume in the respective control-1990 experiments.

To exploit the fact that we needed to run a new spinup-1950 simulation, we introduced additional tuning adjustments in the ocean and sea ice modules originally planned for Phase 2. These include revised parameters for sea ice albedo and thermal conductivity, a new scheme for turbulent kinetic energy penetration below the mixed layer, disabling the implicit top/bottom friction flag, and switching from no-slip to free-slip lateral momentum boundary conditions. All of these adjustments have been previously tested in the intermediate resolution configuration showing a combined positive effect in reducing key model errors, such as mitigating the important mean state cold bias affecting the current spinup-1950 run, which is particularly strong in the Arctic region (Figure 2.1.4.1.3). Due to the cold bias, the spin-up run exhibits a strong cooling trend in the upper ocean (Figure 2.1.4.1.4) in the first two decades after initialization, although by the end of the run those upper levels seem to have stabilised. This is not the case for the ocean levels below 500m, both in terms of global temperature and salinity means, which are still drifting - as we would expect, given that we know the spin up period is far too short to equilibrate the deep ocean. As for the atmosphere, Gregory plots (Figure 2.1.4.1.5) for the spin up run show that after the first decade the model transitions to a state in which the heat budget at the top of the atmosphere is nearly equilibrated, as expected for the fixed 1950 radiative forcing conditions, which gives confidence on the atmospheric model configuration. We have also checked how the model represents in the spin up run two key modes of climate variability. The regression pattern between the North Atlantic Oscillation index and winter sea level pressure shows very good resemblance with the one derived from ERA5 fields. There is also a good agreement with ERA5 for the regression of ENSO with the sea surface temperature fields, although in this case the model shows some errors in the western tropical Pacific, due to an overly extended westward representation of ENSO's pattern. Despite this problem, which is known

to affect many global climate models, the results suggest that IFS-NEMO yields a reasonable representation of the two climate modes dominating the variability in the Euro Atlantic sector and the Tropical Pacific, with well-known remote climate impacts, supporting its future use to assess regional climate change. We still need to confirm if similarly good results also yield for the updated configuration used in the new spin up run.

Figure 2.1.4.1.3: Mean state bias in the seasonal surface air temperature for the last 10 years of Phase 1 IFS-NEMO spinup-1950 experiment. The reference dataset is ERA5.

Figure 2.1.4.1.4: *Timeseries of the globally averaged potential temperature (left) and practical salinity (right) at several selected ocean levels in Phase 1 IFS-NEMO spinup-1950 experiment. To improve the visibility of the results, both variables are computed as standardised anomalies, with the anomalies computed with respect to the first year of the simulation.*

Figure 2.1.4.1.5: *Gregory plot showing the relationship between the globally averaged surface air temperature and the global net radiation at the top-of-the-atmosphere in monthly (left) and yearly (right) means for Phase 1 IFS-NEMO spinup-1950 experiment. The right-hand panel includes reference values from ERA5 2m temperatures in the period 1980-2010 and CERES net radiation at the top-of-the-atmosphere in the period 2001–2020.*

Figure 2.1.4.1.6: (Left) Correlation map between ENSO and sea surface temperature monthly means in Phase 1 IFS-NEMO spinup-1950 experiment. The contour lines are the correlation values for the model and the filled contours illustrate the difference between the model and the reference correlation map, which is produced with ERA5. (Right) The same but between the winter NAO and winter sea level pressures.

2.2 CMIP6-style simulations

2.2.1 Met Office – UM-NEMO

The Met Office model is based on the HadGEM3-GC5 configuration (Xavier et al., in prep). This comprises the Global Atmosphere and Land (GAL9; Willett et al., in prep), the Global Ocean and Sea Ice (GOSI9; Guiavarc’h et al., 2024, submitted), coupled together using the OASIS3-MCT coupler (Ocean Atmosphere Sea Ice Soil Model Coupling Toolkit; Craig et al., 2017). The atmosphere and land components of GC5 run on a staggered latitude–longitude grid using the Met Office Unified Model (MetUM, hereafter simply UM) and JULES (Joint UK Land Environment Simulator; Best et al., 2011) modelling systems respectively. The ocean and sea ice components run on a tripolar grid and are built around the NEMO ocean modelling framework (Madec et al., 2022). The sea ice component of GC5 is the new NEMO sea ice model, SI3 (Sea Ice modelling Integrated Initiative; Vancoppenolle et al., 2023), with its implementation in GC5 documented in Blockley et al., (2024).

The MetUM’s ENDGame dynamical core uses a semi-implicit semi-Lagrangian formulation to solve the non-hydrostatic, fully compressible deep-atmosphere equations of motion (Wood et al., 2014). All configurations use 85 model levels in the vertical. Coupling frequency is one hour, and the full radiation scheme is called every hour. There are very few atmosphere parameter differences between the model resolutions (see Table 2.2.1.1), “two_d_fsd_factor” (overall cloud inhomogeneity parameter) is used to tune the Top-of-Atmosphere (TOA) balance to close to zero (in the pre-

industrial control simulations), while “ussp_launch_factor” helps to correct errors in the QBO frequency. There are other detailed differences in ocean and sea-ice settings, documented in Roberts et al. (2024, in prep) and in the forthcoming EERIE D6.1 deliverable.

Several modifications to the standard HadGEM3-GC5 configuration were made for EERIE, with the model being named HadGEM3-GC5-EERIE. In the MetUM atmospheric component, the standard atmospheric convection scheme has been replaced with the Convective Morphology (CoMorphA) scheme (Lavender et al., 2024; Daleu et al. 2022), which remains as a convective mass flux scheme but replaces the shallow, mid and deep convection of the standard convection scheme (Gregory and Rowntree, 1990). In addition, changes to the ocean bathymetry and other forcing fields were made as part of minor tuning.

Model resolution	Timestep (atm-ocn) (min)	Simulated years/day (SYPD)	Nodes (atm, ocn)	two_d_fsd_factor	ussp_launch_factor
N96-ORCA1 (130 km - 1 degree) - LL	20–60	3.5	25 (16,3)	1.54	1.3
N216-ORCA025 (60 km - 0.25 degree) - MM	15–30	2	107 (70,12)	1.62	1.2
N640-ORCA12 (20 km - 1/12 degree) - HH	10–7.5	0.75	633 (380,180)	1.61	1.2

Table 2.2.1.1: *Some model details for the HadGEM3-GC5-EERIE model simulations. Nodes and SYPD refers to the Cray XC40 machine at the Met Office (36 processors/node).*

As noted above, the length of the piSpinup and piControl simulations needed to be shortened (compared to those typically used in CMIP6) to deliver on EERIE timescales (even so, the piSpinup for HH started before the EERIE project started, in Sept 2022). In addition, the piSpinup for the HH simulation was further optimised by using a lower resolution atmosphere (N216, M) coupled to the eddy-rich ocean (so MH resolution) for the first 200 years, before the H resolution atmosphere was implemented. This made the simulation much faster (about 1.5 years/day rather than 0.75), but unfortunately it did not give the same equilibrium state, and so for the first 50-100 years of the HH piControl aspects of the simulation (such as the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation, AMOC) are still adjusting.

For all resolutions, the ocean component of the coupled model was initialised from the EN4 ocean analysis in 1950 (Good et al., 2013). Unfortunately, we have extremely few observations of the

deep ocean prior to 2004, and hence here (as with all CMIP6 models) the deep ocean is initialised mostly by the present-day ocean, and hence contains far more heat than it should when trying to simulate 1850. This makes the spin-up of the ocean a complex process, as it is difficult (and takes a long time) for the deep ocean to lose heat, and there is no reason to believe that it will lose heat in such a way that the ocean evolves to a state like 1850. This is a problem for the whole of CMIP, and is one of the targets of work within EERIE (WP10 & WP12) to improve the spin-up methodology and save computer time.

The aim of a piSpinup and piControl simulation is to produce a (quasi-)equilibrium state in the coupled climate system with a Top-of-Atmosphere (TOA) radiation balance as near to zero as possible (as it was thought to be in 1850).

2.2.1.1 Met Office results

An upcoming manuscript (Roberts et al., 2024, in prep) will give a full description of the Met Office piControl simulation results, and hence only an overview of the results will be given here.

Figure 1 shows global-mean timeseries of surface air temperature (SAT), TOA, and precipitation averaged between 60S-60N, over the 200 years of piControl simulation. Here we would hope that the TOA would be very close to zero, and the SAT and precipitation would not have any trend over time (i.e., the simulation is in quasi-equilibrium). For the TOA, all three resolutions are indeed close to zero TOA (0.05, 0.08, 0.01 W/m² for LL, MM, HH respectively) and do not show any obvious trend over time. However, for the HH model there does seem to be some trend at least in the earlier period of simulation, in both SAT and precipitation, with quasi-equilibrium achieved after perhaps ~150 years. The LL and MM models show variability in SAT and precipitation, but little if any trend. As noted in D9.3, the precipitation amount in the HadGEM3-GC5 model is higher than that found in observations, and also increases with resolution, and further analysis is needed to better understand the causes.

Fig. 2.2.1.1.1: Timeseries of annual mean (top) global surface air temperature, (middle) global top-of-atmosphere radiation and (bottom) 60S–60N averaged precipitation for the three model resolutions for the piControl simulation.

The evolution of the global ocean from the initial condition, through both the piSpinup and piControl, is shown in Fig. 2.2.1.1.2 for both conservative temperature and absolute salinity. At all resolutions, the ocean rapidly cools over the top 300 m, which is a response to having initial conditions representative of the near-present day ocean, but forcing from 1850. For HH, there is a

reduction in this cool surface layer at around year 200, which corresponds to when the atmosphere resolution was changed from N216 (MH) to N640 (HH). The MM model also seemed to have slightly reduced cooling around year 180, though the reason for this is less clear. For salinity, all the models freshen over time in the top 300 m, with an increase in salinity around 1000 m, stronger at lower resolution. Overall, the differences from the initial condition are smaller in the higher resolution models than LL, and indeed by the end of the piControl the HH model is (globally-averaged) not very different from the initial conditions (at least in temperature).

Fig. 2.2.1.1.2: Time-depth global area-averaged means of (left) conservative temperature and (right) absolute salinity shown as a difference from the initial condition at the start of the piSpinup, over the 240 years of piSpinup and 200 years of piControl. (a) LL, (b) MM and HH resolutions.

Timeseries of the sea-ice concentration are shown in Fig. 2.2.1.1.3 for the Arctic, Antarctic and Weddell Sea. Here the lowest resolution agrees best with observations, while the HH model is well outside the observed sea ice values. As above, when switching from the MH to HH resolution during the piSpinup (around year 200), there is a clear drop in the amount of Antarctic Sea ice, and

although it recovers for a time, it eventually ends up much lower. This is due to a polynya opening in the Weddell Sea, which is (locally) caused by ocean mixing beginning to entrain warm, saline water from deeper in the water column into the cold, fresh surface layer. This causes a feedback process, melting the sea ice, encouraging more deep mixing (due to the surface fluxes now able to act directly on the ocean), and gradually changing the ocean vertical structure. There is ongoing work to better understand this process, but it will not be fixed for this simulation.

Fig. 2.2.1.1.3: Timeseries of sea-ice concentration over piSpinup and piControl simulations for Arctic, Antarctica and Weddell Sea regions. The blue colours are LL, red colours are MM and green colours are MH/HH resolutions, grey line is HadISST observations 1870-present.

The sea surface temperature differences in the piControl simulations compared to the HadISST climatology over 1870-1900 (Rayner et al., 2003) is shown in Fig. 2.2.1.1.4. In the lower latitudes, the models at higher resolution are warmer than LL, and generally have a reduced bias. However, at mid-to-high latitudes, the higher resolution models have a warm bias, which is most obvious in the Southern Ocean and subpolar North Atlantic. A similar pattern was seen in the hierarchy of HighResMIP simulations using a previous version of HadGEM3-GC3.1 (Roberts et al., 2019), and also seems to be a common issue with higher resolution models. Hypotheses for this issue would include: improvements in e.g. large-scale ocean transports (for example Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation, AMOC) at high resolution lead to increased poleward heat transports, but we still lack understanding in how tuning in these models should differ from lower resolutions; compensating errors at low resolution no longer compensate at higher resolution, leading to larger biases in some regions; interactions between atmosphere, ocean and sea ice at higher resolution are different (due to the mesoscale), and this causes biases. We hope within EERIE to begin to understand some of the reasons for these issues, and perhaps some suggested solutions.

Fig. 2.2.1.1.4: Sea surface temperature from piControl simulations averaged over 30 years. (top row) Difference between models and HadISST (averaged over 1870-1900), lower rows differences between indicated model resolutions.

3 Data formats and availability

Data access is much the same as documented in the M7 milestone, but repeated here for completeness.

In order to make data available to internal users from the model simulations as quickly as possible, data at the two central data centres JASMIN and DKRZ/Levante are made available through a central, version controlled [intake](#) catalogue. Data transfer from EERIE data centres to clients is enabled by exposing the data through two protocols, the generic http and the high-performance gridftp. While the first protocol enables a cloud-like data access for interactive usage, gridftp can be used to replicate large volumes of data at a single location. In combination, this enables users to perform efficient data analysis at a central facility.

HTTP access is realised by data servers set-up at the data centres where the model output is produced. A state-of-the-art server at DKRZ, designated for EERIE data and named '[eerie.cloud](#)', enables chunk-based access of EERIE data in the Zarr format. On JASMIN, data from the Met Office simulations is being made available when requested by the users. In contrast to storing the data in an actual cloud storage, this avoids duplication and reformatting. A user guide for the [eerie.cloud](#) is published on [easy.gems](#).

Globus servers existing at the data centres are equipped with gridftp support, and their collections could be successfully extended by EERIE data. Globus was used to replicate EERIE data from other data centres to the one where data is analysed. As DKRZ provided the resources for the EERIE hackathon in Nov 2023, simulations performed for this event were collected and prepared on DKRZ's High Performance File System of the Supercomputer Levante.

To simplify, structure and generalise the EERIE data access, the EERIE data is catalogued. An intake data catalogue for EERIE data has been established allowing users to discover and browse all available data on both systems, Levante and JASMIN. In a collaborative effort, we agreed on a path template for sub-catalogs similar to the CMIP Data Reference Syntax. The catalogue is published and maintained on [github](#). Regular updates keep the catalogue synced whenever data is post processed (e.g. compressed) or more data becomes available from any modelling groups. A user guide is prepared on [easy.gems](#) featuring interactive elements like a [browsable table](#) for convenience.

EERIE data is prepared before being referenced in the catalogue. A workflow is developed and applied which contains [kerchunking](#) of EERIE data in any format to enable access through zarr. Besides the unified access, this includes many advantages for data analysis:

1. Immediate opening of all EERIE data as xarray datasets due to zarr's metadata separation.
2. Minimal memory requirement for opening data due to lazy data access.

3. Large aggregated dataset definitions to minimise data preprocessing tasks.
4. Chunk-based data access, allowing users to get exactly what they want.

The preparation, cataloguing and exposing of data all scales well and new data can easily be included in the catalogue and data servers.

For data from the BSC simulations, the plan involves sharing the data as CMORized netcdf files through BSC's ESGF node, and hence data will be available via the standard CMIP-ESGF replication function. The functionalities to cmorize the data on-the-fly have just been developed and are being thoroughly tested. The data can also be shared via BSC's ftp server, upon user request. Outputs for a selection of popular variables could also be transferred to jasmin/DKRZ machines to facilitate their use.

4 Issues

As noted in the Technical Report, some of the WP3 tasks developing workflows to make data access as simple as possible have been delayed due to one of the WP3 co-leads (Jon Seddon, Met Office) being engaged with the new supercomputer and its data archive solution – with the archive being a necessary condition to enable the full capacity of the new supercomputer.

As noted through this document, there have been considerable challenges in developing the eddy-rich global coupled climate models to produce multi-decadal to centennial simulations, and hence the Phase 1 simulations are behind schedule. However, it is hoped that all models are now configured and ongoing to complete these simulations, and any lessons learnt will be applied when we consider what the Phase 2 simulations should include.

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Acronyms

CMIP:	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project
CMOR:	Climate Model Rewriter
DECK:	Diagnostic, Evaluation and Characterisation of Klima
ESGF:	Earth System Grid Federation
HighResMIP:	High Resolution Model Intercomparison Project